

THE IMPORTANCE OF ULTRASOUND MONITORING IN EARLY DIAGNOSIS AND SELECTION OF REHABILITATION TACTICS FOR POST-INJURY INFLAMMATORY COMPLICATIONS OF THE KNEE JOINT

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Objective of the study: To use ultrasound examination for early detection of inflammatory complications after knee joint injuries - synovitis, bursitis, periarticular edema, hemarthrosis, and inflammatory changes around the meniscus; to assess their severity; and to study the significance of ultrasound monitoring in selecting rehabilitation tactics and stages of physical load.

Keywords: knee joint, ultrasound examination, synovitis, bursitis, hemarthrosis, periarticular swelling, rehabilitation, inflammation, dynamic monitoring.

Materials and methods of research: The study involved 124 patients who presented with signs of inflammation following knee joint injuries. Patients aged 18-60 years exhibited the following complications: synovitis - 54 patients, bursitis - 33 patients, hemarthrosis - 16 patients, and periarticular edema - 21 patients. Ultrasound examination was performed using B-mode, Doppler, and dynamic observation. Rehabilitation approaches were tailored to the type of complication: cryotherapy, phonophoresis, NMES, muscle stabilization, joint mobilization, and gradual load increase, with adjustments made under ultrasound guidance. The examination was conducted at T0 (initial post-injury), T1 (2-3 weeks), T2 (6 weeks), and T3 (9-10 weeks) stages.

Research results: Ultrasound examination demonstrated high sensitivity in the early detection of inflammatory processes. In synovitis, the thickness of the synovial membrane decreased on average from 3.8 mm to 1.7 mm, and exudate regression was fully observed in 79% of patients by the T2 stage. The decrease in Doppler flow provided reliable information about the early subsidence of inflammation. In bursitis, the periarticular fluid layer decreased from 6.1 mm to

1.5 mm, and Doppler signals decreased as early as the T1 stage in 65% of patients. This allowed for early increase in load. In cases of hemarthrosis, the amount of blood and fluid in the joint cavity decreased from 8.6 mm to 1.8 mm. Early detection of hematoma by ultrasound became the basis for modifying the rehabilitation program - delaying the load and early application of NMES. In periarticular inflammation, the degree of muscle atrophy, fascial thickening, and edema was clearly recorded using ultrasound, and a strategy for gradual muscle loading was determined. According to the overall final assessment, the indicators of functional recovery in patients with the chosen rehabilitation tactics based on ultrasound were observed in the range of 85-93%. The ability to timely stop, reduce, or increase the exercise load through ultrasound monitoring helped to reduce the duration of rehabilitation by an average of 20-25%.

Conclusion: Ultrasound monitoring is considered the most effective, early-yielding, and safe diagnostic method for detecting inflammatory complications after knee joint injuries, assessing their severity, and selecting rehabilitation tactics. The real-time accuracy of ultrasound has significant clinical importance in individualizing the rehabilitation process, preventing the consequences of improper loading, and reducing recovery time. Therefore, it is recommended to use ultrasound monitoring as a key component of the rehabilitation strategy for inflammatory complications following knee joint injuries.

